

Ancestor's Formula

Have you ever wanted to know how many greater grandparents did you have? Well, you understand that your parents are your first generation, and the number of your parents are 2. Likewise, your grandparents are your second generation, and the number of your grandparents were 4. This is because your father had 2 parent and so is your mother. Similarly, each of your grandparent had 2 parents which makes the number of your greater grandparents 8.

Understanding the Relation

Now, you understand that this relation is an exponential relation that will keep multiplying by 2. To calculate the number of your ancestors. You will use the relation $g = 2^p$ where g is the number of your ancestors and p is the number of the generation. Keep in mind that this relation cannot be a negative number, a fraction, or an irrational number. p has to be a positive number in order for you to calculate your ancestors. This is because the negative indicates your grandchildren not your ancestors, besides that we won't know the numbers of children we will have. The generation number also cannot be a negative number because the number of ancestors will be a fraction, and it cannot be a fraction or an irrational number because we are counting a human. It makes no sense for everyone to count a human as a decimal or a fraction. The generation number cannot be a fraction or an irrational number because it makes no sense for a generation number to be a decimal or a fraction. This explains that the p has to be a natural number which automatically makes the variable g a natural number.

Sample Problem	
<p>A girl who is obsessed with history and biology overthinks and wants to know how many great great grandparents did she have. Calculate the number of her ancestors.</p> <p>Given $p = 4$</p> <p>Required g</p> <p>Analysis She wants to calculate the number of her great great grand parents which is the 4th generation.</p>	<p>She wants to calculate her 4th generation ancestors. By using $g = 2^p$, we will be able to figure out how many ancestors did she have in the 4th generation.</p> <p>Solution Substitute 4 in p making $p = 4$, and solve for g.</p> <p>$g = 2^4$ $g = 16$</p> <p>Statement The number of ancestors she had in the 4th generation was 16.</p>

The Corruption of the Ancestors' Number

Now, you know how to calculate your ancestors using $g = 2^p$. This also means that you multiply by 2 the far you go with the generation number. However, it might not be working for some people as they have a generation issue. This happens because of the resemblance of each parent. For example, there are people whom their parents are cousins. In this case, you will realize that their 3rd generation will equal to 6 and not 8. This makes $g = 2^p$ an inaccurate

formula to use in calculating the ancestors because $2^3 \neq 6$. There must be a formula that includes a cousin spouse when calculating the ancestor's formula.

What makes it barely true is if the corruption is in the 3rd generation due to the cousin parents, this makes the grandmother from the mother or the father side is either the sibling of the grandmother from the other parent side or the grandfather from the other parent side. As shown in **Figure 1**, this explains how the 3rd generation will have 6 parents instead of 8 like other people.

Figure 1: The grandfather mom side and the grandmother dad side are siblings which makes the 3rd generation have 6 ancestors instead of 8.

This makes us multiply by 2 starting from 6 making the 4th generation 12, and the 5th generation 24 and so on. It's not just $g = 2^p - 2$. The reason is $2^4 - 2$ should equal to 12. However, it equals 14. This makes the formula if the first-generation parents are cousins $g = 2^{p+3} - 2(2^p)$ and p here indicates the generation number starting

from the 3rd generation since we all know that the first-generation ancestors are 2 and the second-generation ancestors were 4.

The Upgraded Ancestor's Formula

This solves the issue of the cousin parents. As shown in Figure 2, the multiplying starts from 6 till infinity. However, the grandparents might be cousin. Not all of them, but it might be either from the dad side, or the mom side. This makes the ancestor's corruption starts from the 4th generation making the ancestors 14 not 12 or 16. The equation will change to $g = 2^{p+4} - 2(2^p)$ which indicates the number of the ancestors starting from the 4th generation if the grandparents (one parent side) were cousins. What if all of the 4 grandparents were cousins. This changes the equation to $g = 2^{p+4} - 4(2^p)$ which makes the ancestors of the 4th generation 12 not 14 as the previous equation. Hence, this makes some constant numbers in the equation should be variables.

Figure 2: Starting from the 3rd generation the ancestors will be 6, and then the further the generation number becomes starting from the 3rd generation, the more we multiply by 2. Making the 4th generation 12.

This creates a new formula with new variables and it can be used to calculate the number of the ancestors whether the ancestors were cousins or not. The formula states that $g = 2^{p+v} - 2\gamma 2^p$ where the v is the number of the corrupted generation such that it cannot be 1 or 2, p indicates that starting point of counting the ancestors, and the γ indicates the number of parents (as a one group) were lost due to the corruption.

$$g = 2^{p+v} - 2\gamma 2^p$$

$$v \neq \{1, 2\}$$

Note: The variables can neither be a fraction nor an irrational number

The reason why v cannot be 1 or 2 is that we all know that the previous generation numbers before the corrupted generation had their fixed numbers of the ancestors.

The upcoming sample problem will help you get the formula since it can be hard for most of the people to understand how it works.

Sample Problem	
If you watch "The Game" series, you will be able to get this sample problem. If Karima	El-Serety and Karim Mahfouz are spouse and they have a child who loves calculating

the ancestor's formula, and he wants to calculate the number of his ancestors in the 5th generation. Calculate the number of his ancestors in the 5th generation.

Given

$$p = 2; v = 3; \gamma = 1$$

Required

g

Analysis

Since Karima and Karim are cousins, their child will share 2 grandparents who are sisters. Shima, and Israa. This means that his great grandparents will be 1 group of parents = 2 parents less than the regular number of the great grandparent making $\gamma = 1$. The child also wants to count his fifth-generation starting from the corrupted generation which is the third-generation. Making the $p = 2$. This also makes $v = 3$ since the corrupted generation is

the 3rd generation. We will use $g = 2^{p+v} - 2\gamma 2^p$ to solve the problem.

Solution

Let's substitute the variables and solve for g .

$$g = 2^{2+3} - 2(1)2^2$$

$$g = 2^5 - 2(2^2)$$

$$g = 32 - 2(4)$$

$$g = 32 - 8$$

$$g = 24$$

Statement

The number of the ancestors of the child of Karima and Karim in the 5th generation were 24.

Summary

- The number of the ancestors can be determined by the equation $g = 2^p$.
- The equation $g = 2^p$ doesn't work on the parents who are cousins.
- There is an extended form of the formula which is $g = 2^{p+v} - 2\gamma 2^p$ where v is the number of the corrupted generation such that it cannot be 1 or 2, p indicates that starting point of counting the ancestors, and the γ indicates the number of parents (as a one group) were lost due to the corruption.

Optional Questions

1. Your grandparents are all cousins and you want to determine the number of your ancestors in the 7th generation. Calculate the number of the ancestors.
2. You grabbed your calculator and you calculated the number of your ancestors and you found out that they were 64 ancestors. Determine the generation number
3. Your grandparent dad side were cousins. You found out that you lost a pair of parents which are 2 parents. After you calculated the number of the ancestors, you found out that they were 56 ancestors. Determine the starting point and the generation number.
4. Why $g = 2^{p+v} - 2\gamma 2^p$ can also be used even if there is no ancestor's corruption?